

MULTI-SCALE APPROACH FOR MULTI-PHASE TRANSPORT IN POROUS MEDIA USING STOCHASTIC PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Fully Lagrangian particle methods have been investigated extensively for single-phase tracer transport in porous media. Here, we introduce a scheme to solve saturation transport equations for two-phase immiscible flow. Note that two types of particles are present, one for each phase, such that each particle represents a physical mass of a single phase. Our motivation is to develop a methodology based on transport of nominal phase particles, which can incorporate pore-scale physical processes in form of Lagrangian statistics obtained from experiments or from pore-scale simulations. In this preliminary paper, we present a simplified version of the method in order to focus on the treatment of nonlinear fluxes. Our numerical experiments show that the particle method can mimic the solution of the standard saturation equation with non-negligible capillary effects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Particle tracking methods have successfully been employed in subsurface flow simulations. Several Eulerian-Lagrangian schemes have been introduced for linear tracer transport (see, e.g., Pollock 1988; Goode 1990; Celia et al. 1990; Konikov et al. 1996; Russell and Celia 2002) and extended to nonlinear problems such as solving the saturation equation for two-phase immiscible flow (see, e.g., Dahle et al. 1990; Dahle et al. 1995; Hewett and Yamada 1997). From the pioneering works of Ahlstrom et al. (1977) and Prickett (1981), fully Lagrangian schemes based on random walk has been widely employed for tracer transport. Here, in contrast to Eulerian-Lagrangian methods, each particle represent a physical mass of tracer and do not simply transport a concentration value. Fully Lagrangian methods have also been applied to reactive-tracer transport with nonlinear accumulation term (see, e.g., Herzer and Kinzelbach 1989; Abulaban et al. 1998; or Delay et al. 2005 for a comprehensive review), which requires the calculation of concentration at the node of a superimposed grid (Bagtzoglou et al. 1992).

To our knowledge, fully Lagrangian methods have not yet been applied to subsurface-flow problems with nonlinear fluxes. Here, we introduce a scheme to solve saturation transport equations for two-phase immiscible flow. Note that two types of particles are present, one for each phase, such that each particle represents a physical mass of a single phase. Our motivation is to develop a methodology based on transport of nominal phase particles, which can incorporate pore-scale physical processes in form of Lagrangian statistics obtained from experiments or from pore-scale simulations. The particle velocity,

for instance, can be described by a given probability-density function (pdf and spatial correlation tensor) such that particles undergo a consistent stochastic motion. Such a framework can naturally deal with compositions and chemical reactions.

In this preliminary paper, however, we present a simplified version of the method and focus on the description of a scheme which guarantees that the total particle flux is consistent with the total-velocity field determined by the pressure solution. First particles are moved deterministically (δ -Dirac shaped pdf) and then the position is stochastically corrected to obtain the correct total particle flux. Here, the goal is to show that the particle method is consistent with the standard saturation equation for two-phase flow. At the point, nonlinear diffusion due to capillarity is modeled by random walk (together with a correction term). It has to be mentioned that a minimum amount of dispersion is required in order to obtain the correct entropy solution.

2. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In this section, we describe the new particle based modeling framework for the study of multi-phase transport in porous media. Therefore, in order to explain the basic ideas, we consider the transport equations

$$\Phi \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (\lambda_1 \nabla p_1) = 0 \quad (1)$$

and

$$\Phi \frac{\partial S_2}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (\lambda_2 \nabla p_2) = 0 \quad (2)$$

for incompressible two-phase flow without gravity effects, where $S_{1,2}$ and $p_{1,2}$ are phase saturations and pressures, respectively, $\lambda_{1,2} = k_{r_{1,2}} k / \mu_{1,2}$ mobilities and Φ the porosity. The relative permeabilities, $k_{r_{1,2}}$, are functions of saturation, the rock permeability, k , a function of space and the viscosities, $\mu_{1,2}$, are constant. The difference between the phase pressures due to capillarity effects is given by the algebraic expression

$$p_1 - p_2 = p_c = c/S_2. \quad (3)$$

With relation (3) Eq. (2) can be rearranged and one obtains

$$\Phi \frac{\partial S_2}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (\lambda_2 \nabla p_1) = -\nabla \cdot (\lambda_2 \nabla p_c) = \nabla \cdot \left(c \frac{\lambda_2}{S_2^2} \nabla S_2 \right) \quad (4)$$

with a diffusion term on the right-hand side. Finally, the sum of Eqs. (1) and (4) results in the pressure equation

$$-\nabla \cdot ((\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \nabla p_1) = \nabla \cdot \left(c \frac{\lambda_2}{S_2^2} \nabla S_2 \right) \quad (5)$$

for p_1 and with the definition of the total flux

$$u^{tot} = -(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \nabla p_1 - c \frac{\lambda_2}{S_2^2} \nabla S_2 \quad (6)$$

and the fractional flow functions

$$f_{1,2} = \frac{\lambda_{1,2}}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2} \quad (7)$$

the saturation equations can be written in the form

$$\Phi \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (f_1 u^{tot}) = \nabla \cdot \left(f_1 \frac{c\lambda_2}{S_2^2} \nabla S_1 \right) \quad (8)$$

and

$$\Phi \frac{\partial S_2}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (f_2 u^{tot}) = \nabla \cdot \left(f_1 \frac{c\lambda_2}{S_2^2} \nabla S_2 \right). \quad (9)$$

Note that $\nabla \cdot u^{tot} \equiv 0$ and $f_1 + f_2 \equiv 1$. Next, we describe how Eqs. (8) and (9) can be solved with a particle method.

3. STOCHASTIC PARTICLE METHOD

The motivation for a Lagrangian simulation framework is to model complex phenomena, which are difficult to treat with an Eulerian approach. At this point, however, the goal is to show that the method presented in this section satisfies local mass balance and converges to the correct solution. Lets consider a large number of computational particles, which represent small fluid volumes belonging either to phase one or phase two. A particle evolution, which is consistent with Eqs. (8) and (9), is given by

$$dx^* = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{f_1 u^{tot}}{\Phi S_1} + \nabla \left(f_1 \frac{c\lambda_2}{\Phi S_2^2} \right) \right) dt + \left(f_1 \frac{c\lambda_2}{2\Phi S_2^2} dt \right)^{1/2} \xi, & \text{if } s^* = 0 \\ \left(\frac{f_2 u^{tot}}{\Phi S_2} + \nabla \left(f_1 \frac{c\lambda_2}{\Phi S_2^2} \right) \right) dt + \left(f_1 \frac{c\lambda_2}{2\Phi S_2^2} dt \right)^{1/2} \xi, & \text{if } s^* = 1, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where x^* is the particle position. The saturation S_2 is the average of the property s^* , which denotes to which phase the particle belongs ($s^* = 0$ and $s^* = 1$ for phase one and two, respectively). Note that random walk (the terms with the normally distributed random variable ξ) is employed to partly account for the terms on the right-hand side of Eqs. (8) and (9). Together with the term $\nabla(f_1 c\lambda_2 / (\Phi S_2^2)) dt$ in Eq. (10) diffusion is treated correctly and as expected, the expectation of the total particle flux is

$$\Phi(S_1 \langle dx^* | s^* = 0 \rangle + S_2 \langle dx^* | s^* = 1 \rangle) / dt = u^{tot}. \quad (11)$$

The operators $\langle \cdot \rangle$ and $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$ denote expectation and conditional expectation, respectively. Numerically, however, S_1 has to be approximated by an estimate $\bar{S}_1 = 1 - \bar{S}_2$ and the numerical expectation of the total particle flux becomes

$$\Phi(S_1 \langle dx^* | s^* = 0 \rangle + S_2 \langle dx^* | s^* = 1 \rangle) / dt = u^{tot} \left(f_1(\bar{S}_1) \frac{S_1}{\bar{S}_1} + f_2(\bar{S}_2) \frac{S_2}{\bar{S}_2} \right), \quad (12)$$

which only is equal to u^{tot} , if $\bar{S}_2 = S_2$, where S_2 is the exact expectation of s^* (the discretization error of the operator ∇ is neglected here). In general, this numerical mass balance inconsistency leads to huge errors. Next, it is shown how this can be avoided with a simple correction scheme.

3.1. Local Mass Balance. We consider the particle evolution given by Eq. (10) while using the numerical approximation $\bar{S}_{1,2} \approx S_{1,2}$. The resulting particle displacement is denoted by dx_u^* . The goal is to come up with a correction dx_c^* , such that local mass balance is achieved. We propose

$$dx_c^* = \begin{cases} \frac{u^{tot}}{\Phi} \left(1 - \frac{f_1(\bar{S}_1)}{S_1}\right) dt, & \text{if } a^* = 0 \\ \frac{u^{tot}}{\Phi} \left(1 - \frac{f_2(\bar{S}_2)}{S_2}\right) dt, & \text{if } a^* = 1, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where $a^* \in \{0, 1\}$ is an independent random variable with $\langle a^* \rangle = S_2$. Note that the numerical expectation of the total particle flux based on the velocity $v^* = (dx_u^* + dx_c^*)/dt$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(S_1 \langle v^* | s^* = 0 \rangle + S_2 \langle v^* | s^* = 1 \rangle) &= u^{tot} (f_1(\bar{S}_1) \frac{S_1}{S_1} + f_2(\bar{S}_2) \frac{S_2}{S_2}) \\ &+ u^{tot} \left(1 - f_1(\bar{S}_1) \frac{\langle 1 - a^* \rangle}{S_1} + f_2(\bar{S}_2) \frac{\langle a^* \rangle}{S_2}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

which becomes equal to u^{tot} provided the relation $\langle a^* \rangle = S_2 = \langle s^* \rangle$ is valid. Another requirement for a^* is independence of s^* . Honoring these two constraints for a^* is crucial, but not straightforward. Here, we explain how this can be achieved. We first consider the hypothetical case with an infinite number of particles. Since $S_2(x) = \langle s^* \rangle(x)$, it is natural to set a^* equal to the property s^* of a randomly chosen particle located at x . In practical cases with finite particle numbers this procedure can be replaced by randomly picking a particle among the n nearest neighbors. Provided the particle number is large enough, the corresponding value of s^* can be regarded as a quasi-random number, which approximately fulfills the requirements for a^* . For all our test cases this method to determine a^* proved very successful. Next, it is shown that the particle displacement $dx_u^* + dx_c^*$ is consistent with the saturation equations (8) and (9).

3.2. Consistency. If one neglects the discretization error of the ∇ -operator, the expected flux of particles with $s^* = 0$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi S_1 \langle v^* | s^* = 0 \rangle &= u^{tot} f_1(\bar{S}_1) \frac{S_1}{S_1} \\ &+ u^{tot} S_1 \left(1 - f_1(\bar{S}_1) \frac{S_1}{S_1} + f_2(\bar{S}_2) \frac{S_2}{S_2}\right) \\ &+ S_1 \nabla \left(f_1(\bar{S}_1) \frac{c\lambda_2(\bar{S}_2)}{S_2^2} \right) - \nabla \left(f_1(\bar{S}_1) \frac{c\lambda_2(\bar{S}_2)}{S_2^2} S_1 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

With the following analysis we show that this flux is consistent with the phase one flux

$$u^1 = u^{tot} f_1 - f_1 \frac{c\lambda_2}{S_2^2} \nabla S_1. \quad (16)$$

Assuming $\bar{S}_{1,2} = S_{1,2} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ one can easily show that for small ε

$$\Phi S_1 \langle v^* |_{s^* = 0} \rangle = u^{tot} f_1(S_1) \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ u^{tot} S_1 (1 - f_1(S_1) + f_2(S_2)) \\ &+ S_1 \nabla \left(f_1(S_1) \frac{c\lambda_2(S_2)}{S_2^2} \right) + \nabla \left(f_1(S_1) \frac{c\lambda_2(S_2)}{S_2^2} S_1 \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) \\ &= u^{tot} f_1(S_1) - f_1(S_1) \frac{c\lambda_2(S_2)}{S_2^2} \nabla S_1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

which is equal to u^1 . Analogously, consistency for the phase two particle flux can be shown. Note that in general $S_{1,2}$ is approximated by kernel function estimates at grid nodes and subsequent interpolation to the particle positions. Therefore, $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ can be expressed as a function of grid spacing h as h^n , where n is some positive number. Next, the time integration scheme used for particle tracking and the overall solution algorithm are described.

3.3. Particle Tracking and Solution Algorithm. The coupled flow and transport problem is solved in a sequential way, i.e. the pressure equation (5) using the estimate $\bar{S}_{1,2} \approx S_{1,2}$ is solved with a classical finite-volume scheme to obtain u^{tot} (from Eq. (6)), which is then used to compute the particle displacements $v^* dt = dx_u^* + dx_c^*$. Here we do not describe the finite-volume scheme used to calculate p_1 , assume however that $\nabla \cdot u^{tot}$ is always zero, except where sources are applied. For particle tracking we use 4th order Runge-Kutta scheme.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we present numerical results of one and two dimensional test cases. The 1D test case is similar to the classical Buckley-Leverett problem except that we consider capillary pressure effect. For the 2D test case we choose a quarter of five spot configuration. The reservoir is initially saturated with phase one, while phase two is injected at one of the corners. In both test cases, quadratic relative permeabilities were used for the two phases, with constant equal viscosities. The numerical values of permeability, porosity and viscosity are equal to unity in all the results presented below.

Fig 1 depicts results from the stochastic particle and finite difference method (SPM and FDM, respectively) for the 1D test case after 0.5s with $u^{tot}=1\text{ms}^{-1}$. Different capillary pressure were used, i.e. $c=0.01\text{Pa}$ for the results in Fig 1a and $c=0.02\text{Pa}$ for the ones in Fig 1b. The reference solution was computed with the FDM using a grid with 2500 nodes (dotted lines). The solid and dashed lines represent the SPM and FDM results, respectively, both based on a grid with 100 nodes. For all SPM simulations the time step size was 0.001s and in order to obtain smooth results 100,000 particles per cell were used. One can easily observe that the SPM gives more accurate results than the FDM at the same grid, although this is not a prime issue discussed here.

Fig 2 depicts the particle number density of the results corresponding to Fig 1a, one (dotted line) with and one (solid line) without correction. It can be seen that the correction reduces the local mass balance error, however, in the case presented the correction appears not to be crucial.

Fig 3 and 4 depict SPM results of the 2D test after 0.25 pore volume injected (PVI). The grid size is 100×100 and the wells are treated as constant source terms uniformly distributed over regions consisting of 10×10 cells at opposite corners. The source strength per unit area is 100s^{-1} and $c=0.04 \text{Pa}$. For this study frozen, but non-uniform velocity field was employed, i.e. the flow was not updated. Note, however, that this poses no limitations.

FIGURE 1. Simulation results of the 1D test case; (a) $c=0.01 \text{Pa}$ and (b) $c=0.02 \text{Pa}$

FIGURE 2. Simulation results of the 1D test case; particle number density with and without correction

FIGURE 3. Simulation results of the 2D test case after 0.25 PVI; (a) saturation contours of the injected phase; (b) particle distribution of the injected phase

FIGURE 4. Simulation results of the 2D test case after 0.25 PVI; saturation surface plot of the injected phase

5. CONCLUSIONS

A stochastic particle framework to model multiphase transport in porous media is presented. This paper shows a proof of concept study, which demonstrates by comparing with finite difference results that the method is accurate, convergent and satisfies local mass balance. In the future we will further generalize this approach to incorporate Lagrangian models for complex multiphase flow.

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